

INSTRUCTIONAL IMPROVEMENT PATHWAYS IN IMPROVING THE STUDENT TASK INTEREST AND TEACHER'S PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

The study attempted to find out the relationship of the instructional improvement pathways to the Student Task Interest and Teachers' Performance in public education. Specifically, it aimed to determine respondent's perception on the instructional improvement pathways as to: Innovative Instruction, Instructional Resources, and Teaching strategies. Secondly, it wanted the student task interest to be measured as to: Performance Output, Attitude, and Reflection. Thirdly, it targeted to measure the extent of teachers' performance of in terms of the domains of teaching. Lastly, it wanted to ascertain if there is a significant relationship between instructional improvement pathways practice and: Student Task Interest; and Teachers' Performance. A descriptive correlational study was employed with a google form questionnaire as instrument. It undergone standard validation and pilot testing. All data were gathered and subjected to statistical analysis. The data showed that teacher respondents "Practiced to Highly Practiced" the statements related to instructional improvement pathways. In terms of the extent of student task interest, a hierarchy of focus is revealed, headlined by Performance output followed by Attitude and Reflection. As to the extent of teachers' performance, teachers' see themselves performing the indicators in the online survey but emphasized assessment and reporting. The data led to the conclusion that instructional improvement pathways practice is significantly related to extent of student task interest and that instructional improvement pathways practice is significantly related to extent of teachers' performance. In line with this, the researcher suggested adoption of instructional improvement pathways practice in private schools as well as integration of student task interest in all learning areas.

Keywords: Improving Student Task Interest, Teacher's Performance, Instructional Improvement Pathways